

GENERALIZED FUZZY Γ -IDEALS OF ORDERED Γ -SEMIGROUPS

AHSAN MAHBOOB* AND NOOR MOHAMMAD KHAN

ABSTRACT. In this paper, the notions of $(\in, \in \vee(k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy left Γ -ideals, $(\in, \in \vee(k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy right Γ -ideals and $(\in, \in \vee(k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy Γ -ideals in ordered Γ -semigroups are introduced and their related properties are investigated. Furthermore, (k^*, k) -lower parts of $(\in, \in \vee(k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy left Γ -ideals, $(\in, \in \vee(k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy right Γ -ideals and $(\in, \in \vee(k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy Γ -ideals are also defined. Finally, left regular, right regular and regular ordered Γ -semigroups in terms of $(\in, \in \vee(k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy left Γ -ideals and $(\in, \in \vee(k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy right Γ -ideals are characterized.

1. INTRODUCTION

In 1986, Sen and Saha [26] introduced the notion of a Γ -semigroup as follows: Let S and Γ be two nonempty sets. Then S is called a Γ -semigroup if there exists a mapping from $S \times \Gamma \times S$ to S which maps $(a, \alpha, b) \rightarrow a\alpha b$ satisfying $(a\gamma b)\mu c = a\gamma(b\mu c)$ for all $a, b, c \in S$ and $\gamma, \mu \in \Gamma$. Later on in 1993, the notion of an ordered Γ -semigroup was introduced by Sen and Seth [27]. Many classical notions such as ideals, bi-ideals and quasi-ideals in ordered semigroups and regular ordered semigroups have been generalized to ordered Γ -semigroups, and these classical notions of ordered Γ -semigroups have been studied by [6, 7, 3, 10, 14]

Zadeh [29], in 1965, introduced the concept of a fuzzy set. The concept of a fuzzy subgroup introduced by Rosenfeld [23]. In 1979, Kuroki [20] introduced fuzzy sets in semigroup theory. Fuzzy sets in ordered semigroups were first studied by Kehayopulu and Tsingelis in [11]. In [28], Tang characterized ordered semigroups by $(\in, \in \vee q)$ -fuzzy ideals. Later on, the concept of $(\in, \in \vee q_k)$ -fuzzy subalgebras in BCK/BCI-algebras is introduced by Jun [1]. In [24] Shabir et al. characterized the regular semigroups by $(\in, \in \vee q_k)$ -fuzzy ideals. In [16, 17, 18] Khan et al characterized ordered semigroups in terms of fuzzy bi-ideals and intuitionistics fuzzy bi-ideals. The concepts $(\in, \in \vee(k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy left ideals, $(\in, \in \vee(k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy right ideals and $(\in, \in \vee(k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy generalized bi-ideals of ordered semigroups are introduced by Khan et al. [13]. Recently, Muhiuddin et al. [21] introduced the concept of $(\in, \in \vee(k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy semiprime ideals using the concept of (k^*, k) quasi-coincidence.

2010 *Mathematics Subject Classification.* 06F05, 08A72.

Key words and phrases. ordered Γ -semigroup; $(\in, \in \vee(k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy left (right) Γ -ideals; $(\in, \in \vee(k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy Γ -ideals.

*Corresponding author.

The $(\in, \in \vee q_k)$ -fuzzy left Γ -ideals, $(\in, \in \vee q_k)$ -fuzzy right Γ -ideals and $(\in, \in \vee q_k)$ -fuzzy ideals of an ordered Γ -semigroup are introduced and characterized by Khan et al. [19]. In [4], Gambo et al. characterized left regular, right regular, regular and completely regular ordered Γ -semigroups in terms of $(\in, \in \vee q_k)$ -fuzzy left Γ -ideals, $(\in, \in \vee q_k)$ -fuzzy right Γ -ideals and $(\in, \in \vee q_k)$ -fuzzy ideals. By generalizing the concept of fuzzy generalized bi Γ -ideals, the concept of $(\in, \in \vee q_k)$ -fuzzy bi Γ -ideals in ordered Γ -semigroups is introduced by Gambo et al. [5].

Motivated by the work of Khan et al. [19] and Gambo et al. [4, 5], in the present paper, we have given some new types of fuzzy left (resp. right) Γ -ideals and Γ -ideals in ordered Γ -semigroups. As a follow up, we introduce the concept of an $(\in, \in \vee (k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy left Γ -ideal, $(\in, \in \vee (k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy right Γ -ideal and $(\in, \in \vee (k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy ideal in an ordered Γ -semigroup, and investigate some vital properties of these new types of fuzzy Γ -ideals. Moreover, we characterize left (resp. right) regular ordered Γ -semigroups in terms (k^*, k) -lower part of $(\in, \in \vee (k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy left (resp. right) Γ -ideals and also regular ordered Γ -semigroups in terms of $(\in, \in \vee (k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy left Γ -ideals and $(\in, \in \vee (k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy right Γ -ideals.

2. PRELIMINARIES

Let S and Γ be the nonempty sets. Then the triplet (S, Γ, \leq) is called an ordered Γ -semigroup if S is a Γ -semigroup and (S, \leq) is a partially ordered set such that

$$a \leq b \Rightarrow a\gamma c \leq b\gamma c \text{ and } c\gamma a \leq c\gamma b$$

for all $a, b, c \in S$ and $\gamma \in \Gamma$.

For a subset A of an ordered Γ -semigroup S , we denote $[A] = \{t \in S \mid t \leq a \text{ for some } a \in A\}$. For any nonempty subsets A and B of S , the following properties hold: (1) $A \subseteq [A]$; (2) $([A]) = [A]$; (3) If $A \subseteq B$, then $[A] \subseteq [B]$; (4) $[A]\Gamma[B] \subseteq [A\Gamma B]$ and (5) $([A]\Gamma[B]) = [A\Gamma B]$.

A nonempty subset T of S is said to be a Γ -subsemigroup of S if for all $x, y \in T$ and $\gamma \in \Gamma$, $x\gamma y \in T$. A nonempty subset A of S is called left (right) Γ -ideal of S if $STA \subseteq A$ ($A\Gamma S \subseteq A$) and $[A] \subseteq A$. If A is both left and right Γ -ideal of S , then A is called a Γ -ideal of S .

Let S be an ordered Γ -semigroup and let A be any nonempty subset of S . Then by $L(A)$, $R(A)$ and $J(A)$, we denote the left Γ -ideal, the right Γ -ideal and the Γ -ideal of S generated by A respectively. It is easy to verify that $L(A) = (A \cup STA)$, $R(A) = (A \cup A\Gamma S)$ and $J(A) = (A \cup STA \cup A\Gamma S \cup STA\Gamma S)$.

Let (S, Γ, \leq) be an ordered Γ -semigroup. A mapping f from S to real closed interval $[0, 1]$ is called the fuzzy subset of S (or fuzzy set of S). We denote by f_A the characteristic function of a subset A of S , which is defined as:

$$f_A(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x \in A \\ 0 & \text{if } x \notin A. \end{cases}$$

For any fuzzy subsets f and g of S , the fuzzy subsets $f \cap g$, $f \cup g$ and $f \circ g$ are defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} (f \cap g)(x) &= \min\{f(x), g(x)\} = f(x) \wedge g(x) \\ (f \cup g)(x) &= \max\{f(x), g(x)\} = f(x) \vee g(x) \end{aligned}$$

and

$$(f \circ g)(x) = \begin{cases} \bigvee_{(y,z) \in A_x} \{f(y) \wedge g(z)\} & \text{if } A_x \neq \phi \\ 0 & \text{if } A_x = \phi, \end{cases}$$

where $A_x = \{(y, z) \in S \times S \mid x \leq y\alpha z \text{ for some } \alpha \in \Gamma\}$. Define an order relation \preceq on the set of all fuzzy subsets of S by

$$f \preceq g \Leftrightarrow f(x) \leq g(x) \text{ for all } x \in S.$$

If f, g are fuzzy subsets of S such that $f \preceq g$, then for each fuzzy subset h of S , $f \circ h \preceq g \circ h$ and $h \circ f \preceq h \circ g$.

A fuzzy subset f of S is called a fuzzy Γ -subsemigroup of S if $f(x\alpha y) \geq \min\{f(x), f(y)\}$ for all $x, y \in S$ and $\alpha \in \Gamma$. A fuzzy subset f of S is called a fuzzy left (resp. right) Γ -ideal of S if (1) $x \leq y \Rightarrow f(x) \geq f(y)$ and (2) $f(x\alpha y) \geq f(y)$ (resp. $f(x\alpha y) \geq f(x)$) for all $x, y \in S$ and $\alpha \in \Gamma$. A fuzzy subset f of S is called a fuzzy Γ -ideal of S if it is both a fuzzy left and right Γ -ideal of S .

Lemma 2.1. [12] *Let S be an ordered Γ -semigroups. Then the following are equivalent:*

- (1) S is regular;
- (2) $A \cap B = (AB)$ for every right ideal A and left ideal B of S .

3. $(\in, \in \vee (k^*, q_k))$ -FUZZY Γ -IDEALS OF ORDERED Γ -SEMIGROUPS

Let S be an ordered Γ -semigroup, $a \in S$ and $u \in (0, 1]$. An ordered fuzzy point a_u is a mapping from S into $[0, 1]$ which is defined as follows:

$$a_u(x) = \begin{cases} u, & \text{if } x \in (a], \\ 0, & \text{if } x \notin (a]. \end{cases}$$

For any fuzzy subset f of S , we shall also denote $a_u \subseteq f$ by $a_u \in f$ in the sequel. Then $a_u \in f$ if and only if $f(a) \geq u$.

An ordered fuzzy point a_u of an ordered Γ -semigroup S is said to be quasi-coincident with a fuzzy subset f of S , written as $a_u q f$, if $f(a) + u > 1$.

Definition 3.1. An ordered fuzzy point x_u of ordered Γ -semigroup S , for any $k^* \in (0, 1]$, is said to be (k^*, q) -quasi-coincident with a fuzzy subset f of S , written as $x_u(k^*, q) f$, if

$$f(x) + u > k^*.$$

Let S be an ordered Γ -semigroup and $0 \leq k < k^* \leq 1$. For an ordered fuzzy point x_u , we say that

- (1) $x_u(k^*, q_k) f$ if $f(x) + u + k > k^*$;
- (2) $x_u \in \vee(k^*, q_k) f$ if $x_u \in f$ or $x_u(k^*, q_k) f$;
- (3) $x_u \bar{\alpha} f$ if $x_u \alpha f$ does not hold for $\alpha \in \{(k^*, q_k), \in \vee(k^*, q_k)\}$.

Definition 3.2. A fuzzy subset f of an ordered Γ -semigroup S is called an $(\in, \in \vee(k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy Γ -subsemigroup of S if $x_u \in f$ and $y_v \in f$ imply $(x\gamma y)_{\min\{u,v\}} \in \vee(k^*, q_k) f$ for all $x, y \in S, \gamma \in \Gamma$ and $u, v \in (0, 1]$.

Definition 3.3. A fuzzy subset f of an ordered Γ -semigroup S is called an $(\in, \in \vee(k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy left (resp. right) Γ -ideal of S if:

- (1) $x \leq y, y_u \in f \Rightarrow x_u \in \vee(k^*, q_k) f$ and
- (2) $x \in S, y_u \in f$ implies $(x\gamma y)_u \in \vee(k^*, q_k) f$ (resp. $(y\gamma x)_u \in \vee(k^*, q_k) f$)

for all $x, y \in S$ and $\gamma \in \Gamma$.

A fuzzy subset f of an ordered Γ -semigroup S is called an $(\in, \in \vee(k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy Γ -ideal if it is both $(\in, \in \vee(k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy left Γ -ideal and $(\in, \in \vee(k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy right Γ -ideal of S .

Example 3.4. Let $S = \{0, w, b, y\}$ and $\Gamma = \{\alpha, \beta\}$ be the nonempty sets. Define binary operations as:

α	0	w	x	y	β	0	w	x	y
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
w	0	x	0	w	w	w	w	w	w
x	0	x	0	y	x	0	0	0	0
y	0	0	0	x	y	w	w	w	y

Define order relation on S as, $\leq := \{(0, 0), (w, w), (x, x), (y, y), (0, w), (0, x), (0, y)\}$. Clearly S is an ordered Γ -semigroup. The fuzzy set $\mu : S \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is defined by

$$\mu(a) = \begin{cases} 0.2 & \text{if } a \in \{0, w, x\} \\ 0 & \text{if } a = y. \end{cases}$$

Take $k^* = 0.5$ and $k = 0.1$. It is easy to verify that μ is an $(\in, \in \vee(k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy left Γ -ideal of S .

Theorem 3.1. Let S be an ordered Γ -semigroup and A be a nonempty subset of S . Then the fuzzy subset f_A of A defined as

$$f_A(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{k^* - k}{2}, & \text{if } x \in A; \\ 0, & \text{if } x \notin A, \end{cases}$$

is an $(\in, \in \vee(k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy left (resp. right) Γ -ideal of S if and only if A is a left (resp. right) Γ -ideal of S .

Proof. Suppose that A is left Γ -ideal of S . Let $x, y \in S$ with $x \leq y$ and $u \in (0, 1]$ such that $y_u \in f_A$. Then $f_A(y) \geq u$. As L is a left Γ -ideal of S , $x \in A$. Thus $f_A(x) = \frac{k^* - k}{2}$. If $u \leq \frac{k^* - k}{2}$, then $f_A(x) \geq u$, so $x_u \in f_A$. If $u > \frac{k^* - k}{2}$, then $f_A(x) + u > \frac{k^* - k}{2} + \frac{k^* - k}{2} = k^* - k$. Thus $x_u(k^*, q_k)f_A$. Therefore $x_u \in \vee(k^*, q_k)f_A$.

Let $x, y \in S$ and $u \in (0, 1]$ such that $y_u \in f$. Then $y \in A$, $f(y) \geq u$. As A is a left Γ -ideal of S , we have $x\gamma y \in A$ for each $\gamma \in \Gamma$. Thus $f(x\gamma y) \geq \frac{k^* - k}{2}$. If $u \leq \frac{k^* - k}{2}$, then $f(x\gamma y) \geq u$. Therefore $(x\gamma y)_u \in f$. Again, if $u > \frac{k^* - k}{2}$, then $f(x\gamma y) + u > \frac{k^* - k}{2} + \frac{k^* - k}{2} = k^* - k$. So $(x\gamma y)_u(k^*, q_k)f$. Therefore $(x\gamma y)_u \in \vee(k^*, q_k)f$.

Conversely, assume that f_A is an $(\in, \in \vee(k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy left Γ -ideal of S . Let $x, y \in S$ such that $x \leq y$. If $y \in A$, then $f_A(y) = \frac{k^* - k}{2}$. As f_A is an $(\in, \in \vee(k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy left Γ -ideal of S and $x \leq y$, we have $f_A(x) \geq \min\{f_A(y), \frac{k^* - k}{2}\} = \frac{k^* - k}{2}$. It follows that $f_A(x) = \frac{k^* - k}{2}$ and so $x \in A$. Let $x \in S$ and $y \in A$. Then $f_A(y) = \frac{k^* - k}{2}$. Now we have

$$f_A(x\gamma y) \geq \min\left\{f_A(y), \frac{k^* - k}{2}\right\} = \frac{k^* - k}{2}.$$

Thus $f_A(x\gamma y) = \frac{k^* - k}{2}$ and so $x\gamma y \in A$. Hence A is a left Γ -ideal of S . \square

Corollary 3.2. Let S be an ordered Γ -semigroup and A be a nonempty subset of S . Then the fuzzy subset f_A of A is defined as

$$f_A(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{k^* - k}{2}, & \text{if } x \in A; \\ 0, & \text{if } x \notin A, \end{cases}$$

is an $(\in, \in \vee(k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy Γ -ideal of S if and only if A is a Γ -ideal of S .

Theorem 3.3. A fuzzy subset f of S is an $(\in, \in \vee(k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy left (resp. right) Γ -ideal of S if and only if

- (1) $x \leq y \Rightarrow f(x) \geq \min\{f(y), \frac{k^*-k}{2}\}$;
- (2) $f(x\gamma y) \geq \min\{f(y), \frac{k^*-k}{2}\}$ (resp. $f(x\gamma y) \geq \min\{f(x), \frac{k^*-k}{2}\}$);

for all $x, y \in S$ and $\gamma \in \Gamma$.

Proof. Let f be an $(\in, \in \vee(k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy left Γ -ideal of S and $x, y \in S$. If $f(x) < \min\{f(y), \frac{k^*-k}{2}\}$ for some $x, y \in S$. Choose $u \in (0, 1]$ such that $f(x) < u \leq \min\{f(y), \frac{k^*-k}{2}\}$. Then $y_u \in f$, but $(x)_u \notin \vee(k^*, q_k)f$, a contradiction. Thus $f(x) \geq \min\{f(y), \frac{k^*-k}{2}\}$. Again, if $f(x\gamma y) < \min\{f(y), \frac{k^*-k}{2}\}$ for some $x, y \in S$ and $\gamma \in \Gamma$. Choose $u \in (0, 1]$ such that $f(x\gamma y) < u \leq \min\{f(y), \frac{k^*-k}{2}\}$. Then $y_u \in f$ but $(x\gamma y)_u \notin \vee(k^*, q_k)f$, which is a contradiction. Hence $f(x\gamma y) \geq \min\{f(y), \frac{k^*-k}{2}\}$.

Conversely assume that $f(x) \geq \min\{f(y), \frac{k^*-k}{2}\}$ for all $x, y \in S$. Let $y_u \in f$ ($u \in (0, 1]$). Then $f(y) \geq u$. So $f(x) \geq \min\{f(y), \frac{k^*-k}{2}\} \geq \min\{u, \frac{k^*-k}{2}\}$. If $u \leq \frac{k^*-k}{2}$, then $f(x) \geq u$ implies $x_u \in f$. Again, if $u > \frac{k^*-k}{2}$, then $f(x) \geq \frac{k^*-k}{2}$. So $f(x) + u > \frac{k^*-k}{2} + \frac{k^*-k}{2} = k^* - k$, which implies that $x_u \in \vee(k^*, q_k)f$. Thus $x_u \in \vee(k^*, q_k)f$. Let $f(x\gamma y) \geq \min\{f(y), \frac{k^*-k}{2}\}$ for all $x, y \in S$ and $\gamma \in \Gamma$. Let $y_u \in f$ ($u \in (0, 1]$). Then $f(y) \geq u$. So $f(x\gamma y) \geq \min\{f(y), \frac{k^*-k}{2}\} \geq \min\{u, \frac{k^*-k}{2}\}$. If $u \leq \frac{k^*-k}{2}$, then $f(x\gamma y) \geq u$ implies $(x\gamma y)_u \in f$. If $u > \frac{k^*-k}{2}$, then $f(x\gamma y) \geq \frac{k^*-k}{2}$. So $f(x\gamma y) + u > \frac{k^*-k}{2} + \frac{k^*-k}{2} = k^* - k$, it follows that $(x\gamma y)_u \in \vee(k^*, q_k)f$. Thus $(x\gamma y)_u \in \vee(k^*, q_k)f$. Hence f is an $(\in, \in \vee(k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy left Γ -ideal of S . \square

Corollary 3.4. A fuzzy subset f of S is an $(\in, \in \vee(k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy Γ -ideal of S if and only if

- (1) $x \leq y \Rightarrow f(x) \geq \min\{f(y), \frac{k^*-k}{2}\}$;
- (2) $f(x\gamma y) \geq \min\{f(y), \frac{k^*-k}{2}\}$ and $f(x\gamma y) \geq \min\{f(x), \frac{k^*-k}{2}\}$;

for all $x, y \in S$ and $\gamma \in \Gamma$.

Definition 3.5. Let f be any fuzzy subset of an ordered Γ -semigroup S . For any $u \in (0, 1]$, the set

$$U(f; u) = \{x \in S \mid f(x) \geq u\},$$

is called a level subset of f .

Theorem 3.5. Let f be a fuzzy subset of S . Then f is an $(\in, \in \vee(k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy left (resp. right) Γ -ideal of S if and only if $U(f; u) (\neq \emptyset)$ ($u \in (0, \frac{k^*-k}{2}]$) is a left (resp. right) Γ -ideal of S .

Proof. Suppose that f is an $(\in, \in \vee(k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy left Γ -ideal of S . Let $x, y \in S$ be such that $x \leq y \in U(f; u)$, where $u \in (0, \frac{k^*-k}{2}]$. Then $f(y) \geq u$. By Theorem 3.3, $f(x) \geq \min\{f(y), \frac{k^*-k}{2}\} \geq \min\{u, \frac{k^*-k}{2}\} = u$. Therefore $x \in U(f; u)$ and $y \in U(f; u)$. Let $x \in S$ and $y \in U(f; u)$. Then $f(x) \geq u$. So, by Theorem 3.3, $f(x\gamma y) \geq \min\{f(y), \frac{k^*-k}{2}\} \geq \min\{u, \frac{k^*-k}{2}\} = u$. Thus $f(x\gamma y) \geq u$. Therefore $x\gamma y \in U(f; u)$. Hence $U(f; u)$ is a left Γ -ideal.

Conversely assume that $U(f; u) (\neq \emptyset)$ is a left Γ -ideal of S for all $u \in (0, \frac{k^*-k}{2}]$. Take any $x, y \in S$ with $x \leq y$. If $f(x) < \min\{f(y), \frac{k^*-k}{2}\}$. Then $f(x) < u \leq \min\{f(y), \frac{k^*-k}{2}\}$, for some $u \in (0, \frac{k^*-k}{2}]$. It follows that $y \in U(f; u)$ but $x \notin U(f; u)$, which is a contradiction. Thus $f(x) \geq \min\{f(y), \frac{k^*-k}{2}\}$ for all $x, y \in S$ with $x \leq y$.

Again, if $f(x\gamma y) < \min\{f(y), \frac{k^*-k}{2}\}$ for some $x, y \in S$. Therefore there exist $u \in (0, \frac{k^*-k}{2}]$ such that $f(x\gamma y) < u \leq \min\{f(y), \frac{k^*-k}{2}\}$ implies $y_u \in U(f; u)$ but $(x\gamma y)_u \notin U(f; u)$, which is again a contradiction. Thus $f(x\gamma y) \geq \min\{f(y), \frac{k^*-k}{2}\}$ for all $x, y \in S$. Hence by Theorem 3.3, f is an $(\in, \in \vee (k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy left Γ -ideal of S . \square

Corollary 3.6. *Let f be a fuzzy subset of S . Then f is an $(\in, \in \vee (k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy Γ -ideal of S if and only if $U(f; u) (\neq \emptyset)$ ($u \in (0, \frac{k^*-k}{2}]$) is a Γ -ideal of S .*

Lemma 3.7. *If f is a nonzero $(\in, \in \vee (k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy left (resp. right) Γ -ideal of S , then the set $f_0 = \{x \in S \mid f(x) > 0\}$ is a left (resp. right) Γ -ideal of S .*

Proof. Let f be an $(\in, \in \vee (k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy left Γ -ideal of S . Let $x, y \in S$, $x \leq y$ and $y \in f_0$. Then $f(y) > 0$. As f is an $(\in, \in \vee (k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy left Γ -ideal of S , $f(x) \geq \min\{f(y), \frac{k^*-k}{2}\} > 0$. Since $f(y) > 0$, we have $f(x) > 0$ and so $x \in f_0$. Let $x \in S$ and $y \in f_0$. Then $f(y) > 0$. Therefore $f(x\gamma y) \geq \min\{f(y), \frac{k^*-k}{2}\} > 0$. Thus $x\gamma y \in f_0$, as required. \square

Corollary 3.8. *If f is a nonzero $(\in, \in \vee (k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy Γ -ideal of S , then the set $f_0 = \{x \in S \mid f(x) > 0\}$ is a Γ -ideal of S .*

4. (k^*, k) -LOWER PARTS OF $(\in, \in \vee (k^*, q_k))$ -FUZZY Γ -IDEALS

Let f be a fuzzy subset of an ordered Γ -semigroup S . The (k^*, k) -lower part $\underline{f}_k^{k^*}$ of f is defined as follows:

$$\underline{f}_k^{k^*}(x) = \min \left\{ f(x), \frac{k^* - k}{2} \right\}$$

for all $x \in S$ and $0 \leq k < k^* \leq 1$.

For any nonempty subset A of S and fuzzy subset f of S , $(\underline{f}_A)_k^{k^*}$, the (k^*, k) -lower part of the characteristic function f_A , will be denoted by $(\underline{f}_k^{k^*})_A$ in the sequel.

Let f and g be any fuzzy subsets of S . Define $f(\cap)_k^{k^*} g$, $f(\cup)_k^{k^*} g$ and $f(\circ)_k^{k^*} g$ as follows:

$$(f(\cap)_k^{k^*} g)(x) = \min \left\{ (f \cap g)(x), \frac{k^* - k}{2} \right\}$$

$$(f(\cup)_k^{k^*} g)(x) = \min \left\{ (f \cup g)(x), \frac{k^* - k}{2} \right\}$$

$$(f(\circ)_k^{k^*} g)(x) = \min \left\{ (f \circ g)(x), \frac{k^* - k}{2} \right\}$$

for all $x \in S$ and $0 \leq k < k^* \leq 1$.

Let f and g be any fuzzy subsets of S . Then we have: (1) $(\underline{f}_k^{k^*})_k^{k^*} = \underline{f}_k^{k^*}$ and $\underline{f}_k^{k^*} \subseteq f$; (2) If $f \subseteq g$, and $h \in F(S)$, then $f(\circ)_k^{k^*} h \subseteq g(\circ)_k^{k^*} h$ and $h(\circ)_k^{k^*} f \subseteq h(\circ)_k^{k^*} g$; (3) $f(\cap)_k^{k^*} g = \underline{f}_k^{k^*} \cap \underline{g}_k^{k^*}$; (4) $f(\cup)_k^{k^*} g = \underline{f}_k^{k^*} \cup \underline{g}_k^{k^*}$; (5) $f(\circ)_k^{k^*} g = \underline{f}_k^{k^*} \circ \underline{g}_k^{k^*}$.

Lemma 4.1. *Let A and B be any nonempty subsets of an ordered Γ -semigroup S . Then*

- (1) $f_A(\cap)_k^{k^*} f_B = (\underline{f}_k^{k^*})_{A \cap B}$;
- (2) $f_A(\cup)_k^{k^*} f_B = (\underline{f}_k^{k^*})_{A \cup B}$;
- (3) $f_A(\circ)_k^{k^*} f_B = (\underline{f}_k^{k^*})_{(A \Gamma B)}$.

Proof. Straightforward. \square

Theorem 4.2. *The (k^*, k) -lower part $(\underline{f_k^{k^*}})_A$ of the characteristic function f_A of a nonempty subset A is an $(\in, \in \vee (k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy left (resp. right) Γ -ideal of S if and only if A is a left (resp. right) Γ -ideal of S .*

Proof. Let A be a left Γ -ideal of S . Let $x, y \in S$, $x \leq y$ and $u \in (0, 1]$ be such that $y_u \in (\underline{f_k^{k^*}})_A$. Then $y \in A$, $(\underline{f_k^{k^*}})_A(y) \geq u$. As A is a left Γ -ideal of S and $x \leq y \in A$, $x \in A$. Thus $f_A(x) \geq \frac{k^* - k}{2}$. If $u \leq \frac{k^* - k}{2}$, then $f_A(x) \geq u$, so we have $x_u \in (\underline{f_k^{k^*}})_A$. If $u > \frac{k^* - k}{2}$, then $f_A(x) + u > \frac{k^* - k}{2} + \frac{k^* - k}{2} = k^* - k$. So $x_u(k^*, q_k) \in (\underline{f_k^{k^*}})_A$. Therefore $x_u \in \vee (k^*, q_k)(\underline{f_k^{k^*}})_A$.

Next suppose that $x \in S, y_u \in (\underline{f_k^{k^*}})_A$ and $\gamma \in \Gamma$. Then $y \in A$, $(\underline{f_k^{k^*}})_A(y) \geq u$. As A is a left Γ -ideal of S , $x\gamma y \in A$. Thus $f_A(x\gamma y) \geq \frac{k^* - k}{2}$. If $u \leq \frac{k^* - k}{2}$, then $f_A(x\gamma y) \geq u$, so $(x\gamma y)_u \in (\underline{f_k^{k^*}})_A$. If $u > \frac{k^* - k}{2}$, then $f_A(x\gamma y) + u > \frac{k^* - k}{2} + \frac{k^* - k}{2} = k^* - k$. So $(x\gamma y)_u(k^*, q_k) \in (\underline{f_k^{k^*}})_A$. Therefore $(x\gamma y)_u \in \vee (k^*, q_k)(\underline{f_k^{k^*}})_A$.

Conversely assume that $(\underline{f_k^{k^*}})_A$ is an $(\in, \in \vee (k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy left Γ -ideal of S . Let $x, y \in S$ such that $x \leq y$. If $y \in A$, then $(\underline{f_k^{k^*}})_A(y) = \frac{k^* - k}{2}$. Since $(\underline{f_k^{k^*}})_A$ is an $(\in, \in \vee (k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy left Γ -ideal of S , and $x \leq y$, we have $(\underline{f_k^{k^*}})_A(x) \geq \min\{(\underline{f_k^{k^*}})_A(y), \frac{k^* - k}{2}\} = \frac{k^* - k}{2}$. It follows that $(\underline{f_k^{k^*}})_A(x) = \frac{k^* - k}{2}$ and so $x \in A$. Let $x \in S$ and $y \in A$. $(\underline{f_k^{k^*}})_A(y) = \frac{k^* - k}{2}$. Now, $(\underline{f_k^{k^*}})_A(x\gamma y) \geq \min\{(\underline{f_k^{k^*}})_A(y), \frac{k^* - k}{2}\} = \frac{k^* - k}{2}$. Hence $(\underline{f_k^{k^*}})_A(x\gamma y) = \frac{k^* - k}{2}$ and so $x\gamma y \in A$. Therefore A is a left Γ -ideal of S . \square

Corollary 4.3. *The (k^*, k) -lower part $(\underline{f_k^{k^*}})_A$ of the characteristic function f_A of a nonempty subset A is an $(\in, \in \vee (k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy Γ -ideal of S if and only if A is a Γ -ideal of S .*

Lemma 4.4. *If f is an $(\in, \in \vee (k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy left (resp. right) Γ -ideal of S , then $\underline{f_k^{k^*}}$ is a fuzzy left (resp. right) Γ -ideal of S .*

Proof. Let $x, y \in S$ such that $x \leq y$. As f is an $(\in, \in \vee (k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy left Γ -ideal of S , $f(x) \geq \min\{f(y), \frac{k^* - k}{2}\}$. It follows that $\min\{f(x), \frac{k^* - k}{2}\} \geq \min\{f(y), \frac{k^* - k}{2}\}$ and so, $(\underline{f_k^{k^*}})(x) \geq (\underline{f_k^{k^*}})(y)$. Let $x, y \in S$ and $\gamma \in \Gamma$, then we have $f(x\gamma y) \geq \min\{f(y), \frac{k^* - k}{2}\}$. Then $\min\{f(x\gamma y), \frac{k^* - k}{2}\} \geq \min\{f(y), \frac{k^* - k}{2}\}$, and so $(\underline{f_k^{k^*}})(x\gamma y) \geq \min\{(\underline{f_k^{k^*}})(y), \frac{k^* - k}{2}\}$. Therefore $\underline{f_k^{k^*}}$ is a fuzzy left Γ -ideal of S . \square

Corollary 4.5. *If f is an $(\in, \in \vee (k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy Γ -ideal of S , then $\underline{f_k^{k^*}}$ is a fuzzy Γ -ideal of S .*

Theorem 4.6. *An ordered Γ -semigroup S is left (resp. right) regular if and only if $(\underline{f_k^{k^*}})(a) = (\underline{f_k^{k^*}})(a\alpha a)$, for each $(\in, \in \vee (k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy left (resp. right) Γ -ideal f of S and for each $a \in S, \alpha \in \Gamma$.*

Proof. Let $a \in S$. As S is left regular, $a \in (S\Gamma a\Gamma a]$. Then there exist $x \in S$ and $\gamma, \beta \in \Gamma$ such that $a \leq x\gamma a\alpha a$. Since f is an $(\in, \in \vee (k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy left Γ -ideal of S , we have

$$\begin{aligned} f(a) &\geq \min \left\{ f(x\gamma a\alpha a), \frac{k^* - k}{2} \right\} \\ &\geq \min \left\{ f(a\alpha a), \frac{k^* - k}{2} \right\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\geq \min \left\{ f(a), \frac{k^* - k}{2} \right\}$$

Therefore $(\underline{f_k^{k^*}})(a) = (\underline{f_k^{k^*}})(a\alpha a)$.

Conversely take any $a \in S, \alpha \in \Gamma$. Consider the left Γ -ideal $L(a\alpha a) = (a\alpha a \cup S\Gamma a\alpha a]$ of S generated by $a\alpha a (a \in S)$. Then, by Theorem 4.2, $(\underline{f_k^{k^*}})_{L(a\alpha a)}$ is an $(\in, \in \vee (k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy left Γ -ideal of S . Therefore by hypothesis, $(\underline{f_k^{k^*}})_{L(a\alpha a)}(a) = (\underline{f_k^{k^*}})_{L(a\alpha a)}(a\alpha a)$. Since $a^2 \in L(a\alpha a)$, we have $(\underline{f_k^{k^*}})_{L(a\alpha a)}(a\alpha a) = \frac{k^* - k}{2}$, and so, $(\underline{f_k^{k^*}})_{L(a\alpha a)}(a) = \frac{k^* - k}{2}$. Thus, $a \in L(a\alpha a)$. Thus $a \leq a\alpha a$ or $a \leq x\gamma a\alpha a$. If $a \leq a\alpha a$, then $a \leq a\alpha a = a\alpha a \leq a\alpha a\alpha a = a\alpha a\alpha a \in S\Gamma a\Gamma a$ and $a \in (S\Gamma a\Gamma a]$. Again, if $a \leq x\gamma a\alpha a$, then $a \in (S\Gamma a\Gamma a]$. So $a \in (S\Gamma a\Gamma a]$. Therefore S is left regular. \square

Theorem 4.7. *The following assertions are equivalent in S :*

- (1) S is regular.
- (2) $f(\circ)_k^{k^*} g = f(\cap)_k^{k^*} g$ for each $(\in, \in \vee (k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy right Γ -ideal f and $(\in, \in \vee (k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy left Γ -ideal g of S .

Proof. (1) \Rightarrow (2). Suppose that f and g are $(\in, \in \vee (k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy right Γ -ideal and an $(\in, \in \vee (k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy left Γ -ideal of S , and $a \in S$. Then there exists $r \in S$ and α, β such that $a \leq ara$, it follows that $(a\alpha r, a) \in A_a$. Then we have

$$\begin{aligned} (f(\circ)_k^{k^*} g)(a) &= \bigvee_{(y,z) \in A_a} \min \left\{ \underline{f_k^{k^*}}(y), \underline{g_k^{k^*}}(z) \right\} \\ &\geq \min \left\{ \underline{f_k^{k^*}}(a\alpha r), \underline{g_k^{k^*}}(a) \right\} \\ &= \min \left\{ f(a\alpha r), \underline{g_k^{k^*}}(a), \frac{k^* - k}{2} \right\} \\ &= \min \left\{ f(a), \underline{g_k^{k^*}}(a), \frac{k^* - k}{2} \right\} \\ &= \min \left\{ \underline{f_k^{k^*}}(a), \underline{g_k^{k^*}}(a) \right\} \\ &= (f(\cap)_k^{k^*} g)(a). \end{aligned}$$

Thus $f(\cap)_k^{k^*} g \subseteq f(\circ)_k^{k^*} g$. Inverse inclusion is obvious. Therefore $f(\cap)_k^{k^*} g = f(\circ)_k^{k^*} g$.

(2) \Rightarrow (1). Suppose that L and R are left and right Γ -ideal of S . Take any $x \in L \cap R$. Then $x \in L$ and $x \in R$. As L is a left Γ -ideal and R is a right Γ -ideal of S , by Theorem 4.2, $(\underline{f_k^{k^*}})_L$ is an $(\in, \in \vee (k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy left Γ -ideal and $(\underline{f_k^{k^*}})_R$ is an $(\in, \in \vee (k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy right Γ -ideal of S . So, we have $(f_R(\circ)_k^{k^*} f_L)(x) \geq (f_R(\cap)_k^{k^*} f_L)(x) = \min \{ (\underline{f_k^{k^*}})_R(x), (\underline{f_k^{k^*}})_L(x) \}$. Since $x \in L$ and $x \in R$, $(\underline{f_k^{k^*}})_L = \frac{k^* - k}{2}$ and $(\underline{f_k^{k^*}})_R = \frac{k^* - k}{2}$. Thus $(f_R(\cap)_k^{k^*} f_L)(x) = \frac{k^* - k}{2}$. Therefore $(f_R(\circ)_k^{k^*} f_L)(x) \geq \frac{k^* - k}{2}$. Since $(f_R(\circ)_k^{k^*} f_L)(x) \leq \frac{k^* - k}{2}$. Therefore $(f_R(\circ)_k^{k^*} f_L)(x) = \frac{k^* - k}{2}$. By Lemma 4.1(3), we have

$$(f_R(\circ)_k^{k^*} f_L)(x) = (\underline{f_k^{k^*}})_{(R\Gamma L)}(x).$$

Therefore, $(\underline{f_k^{k^*}})_{(R\Gamma L)}(x) = \frac{k^* - k}{2}$ and so, $x \in (R\Gamma L)$. It follows that $L \cap R \subseteq (R\Gamma L)$. Also $(R\Gamma L] \subseteq L \cap R$. Thus $L \cap R = (R\Gamma L]$. Hence by Lemma 2.1, S is regular. \square

5. CONCLUSION

The main purpose of the present paper is to introduce the concept of an $(\in, \in \vee(k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy Γ -ideal, $(\in, \in \vee(k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy left Γ -ideal and $(\in, \in \vee(k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy right Γ -ideal in ordered semigroups by generalizing the concept of $(\in, \in \vee q_k)$ -fuzzy Γ -ideal, $(\in, \in \vee q_k)$ -fuzzy left Γ -ideal and $(\in, \in \vee q_k)$ -fuzzy right Γ -ideal. Also, we enhance the understanding of regular ordered Γ -semigroups by considering the structural influence of the $(\in, \in \vee(k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy Γ -ideals, $(\in, \in \vee(k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy left Γ -ideals and $(\in, \in \vee(k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy right Γ -ideals. In our future work, by using the concept of (k^*, q) -quasi-coincident with a fuzzy subset of ordered Γ -semigroups, the concept of $(\in, \in \vee(k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy interior Γ -ideals and $(\in, \in \vee(k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy quasi Γ -ideals of ordered Γ -semigroups will be introduced.

Following are the particular cases of the present paper:

(1). If we take $k^* = 1$, then the definition of an $(\in, \in \vee(k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy Γ -ideal, $(\in, \in \vee(k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy left Γ -ideal and $(\in, \in \vee(k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy right Γ -ideal reduce to a concept and we call as an $(\in, \in \vee q_k)$ -fuzzy Γ -ideal, $(\in, \in \vee q_k)$ -fuzzy left Γ -ideal and $(\in, \in \vee q_k)$ -fuzzy right Γ -ideal. Thus we can apply all the results of this paper in the setting of $(\in, \in \vee q_k)$ -fuzzy Γ -ideals.

(2). If we take $k^* = 1$ and $k = 0$, then the definition of an $(\in, \in \vee(k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy Γ -ideal, $(\in, \in \vee(k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy left Γ -ideal and $(\in, \in \vee(k^*, q_k))$ -fuzzy right Γ -ideal reduce to a concept and we call as an $(\in, \in \vee q)$ -fuzzy Γ -ideal, $(\in, \in \vee q)$ -fuzzy left Γ -ideal and $(\in, \in \vee q)$ -fuzzy right Γ -ideal. Thus all the results of this paper may be applied in the setting of $(\in, \in \vee q)$ -fuzzy (m, n) -ideals.

REFERENCES

- [1] Y. B. Jun. Generalization of $(\in, \in \vee q)$ -fuzzy subalgebras in BCK/BCI-algebras, *Comput. Math. Appl.*, 58 (2009), 1383 – 1390.
- [2] M. Y. Abbasi and A. Basar. Some properties of ordered 0-minimal $(0, 2)$ -bi- Γ -ideals in po- Γ -semigroups, *Hacettepe Journal of Mathematics and Statistics*, 44 (2) (2015), 247-254.
- [3] T. Changphas and B. Thongkam. A Note on Maximal Ideals in Ordered Γ -Semigroups, *International Mathematical Forum*, 6 (2011), 3343-3347.
- [4] I. Gambo, N. H. Sarmin, H. U. Khan and F. M. Khan. The characterization of regular ordered Γ -semigroups in terms of $(\in, \in \vee q_k)$ -fuzzy Γ -ideals, *Malaysian Journal of Fundamental and Applied Sciences*, 13(4) (2017), 576-580.
- [5] I. Gambo, N. H. Sarmin, H. U. Khan and F. M. Khan. New fuzzy generalized bi Γ -ideals of the type $(\in, \in \vee q_k)$ in ordered Γ -semigroups, *Malaysian Journal of Fundamental and Applied Sciences*, 13(4) (2017) 666-670.
- [6] K. Hila. On quasi prime, weakly quasi-prime left ideal in ordered Γ -semigroups, *Mathematical Slovaca*, 60 (2010), 195-212.
- [7] K. Hila and E. Pisha. Characterizations on ordered Γ -semigroup, *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics*, 28 (2006), 423-439.
- [8] K. Hila and E. Pisha. On bi-ideals on ordered Γ -semigroups, *Hacettepe Journal of Mathematics and Statistics*, 40(6)(2011), 793-804.
- [9] A. Iampan. Characterizing Ordered Bi-Ideals in Ordered Γ -Semigroups, *Iranian Journal of Mathematical Sciences and Informatics*, 4 (2009), 17-25.
- [10] A. Iampan. Characterizing intuitionistic fuzzy Γ -Ideals of ordered Γ -semigroups by means of intuitionistic fuzzy points, *Notes on Intuitionistic Fuzzy Sets*, 21(3), 2015, 2439.
- [11] N. Kehayopulu and M. Tsingelis. Fuzzy sets in ordered groupoids, *Semigroup Forum*, 65 (2002), 128 – 132.
- [12] N. Kehayopulu. On Ordered Γ -semigroup, *Scientiae Mathematicae Japonicae Online*, (2010), 37-43.
- [13] N. M. Khan, B. Davvaz and M. A. Khan. Ordered semigroups characterized in terms of generalized fuzzy ideals, *J. Intell. Fuzzy Syst.*, 32(1) (2017), 1045-1057.

- [14] Y. I. Kwon and S. K. Lee. The weakly prime ideals of ordered Γ -semigroups, *Commun. Korean Math. Soc.*, 13 (1998), 251-256.
- [15] Y. I. Kwon and S. K. Lee. Some special elements in ordered Γ -semigroups, *Kyungpook Math. J.*, 35(3) (1996), 679-685.
- [16] A. Khan, Y. B. Jun, N. H. Sarmin and F. M. Khan. Ordered semigroups characterized by $(\in, \in \vee q_k)$ -fuzzy generalized bi-ideals, *Neural Comput. and Applic.*, 21(suppl.) (2012), 121 – 132.
- [17] A. Khan, N. H. Sarmin, B. Davvaz and F. M. Khan. New types of fuzzy biideals in ordered semigroups, *Neural Computing and Applications*, 21 (2012), 295 – 305.
- [18] A. Khan, B. Davvaz, N. H. Sarmin and H. U. Khan. Redefined intuitionistic fuzzy biideals of ordered semigroups, *Journal of Inequalities and Applications*, (2013), 2013, 397.
- [19] F. M. Khan, N. H. Sarmin and A. Khan. A novel approach towards fuzzy Γ -ideals in ordered Γ -semigroups, *Indian Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics*, 45(3) (2014), 343-362.
- [20] N. Kuroki. Fuzzy bi-ideals in semigroups, *Comment. Math. Univ. St. Pauli* 28 (1979), 17 – 21.
- [21] G. Muhiuddin, A. Mahboob and N. M. Khan. A new type of fuzzy semiprime subsets in ordered semigroups, *J. Intell. Fuzzy Syst.*, vol. Pre-press, no. Pre-press, 2019, 1-10.
- [22] P. Pal, S. K. Majumder, B. Davvaz and S. K. Sardar. Regularity of Po- Γ -semigroups in terms of fuzzy subsemigroups and fuzzy bi-ideals, *Fuzzy information and Engineering*, 7 (2015), 165-182.
- [23] A. Rosenfeld. Fuzzy subgroups, *J. Math. Anal. Appl.* 35 (1971), 512 – 517.
- [24] M. Shabir, Y. B. Jun and Y. Nawaz. Characterizations of regular semigroups by $(\in, \in \vee q_k)$ -fuzzy ideals, *Comput. Math. Appl.* 59 (2010), 539 – 549.
- [25] J. Sanborisoot and T. Changphas. On Pure ideals in ordred Ternary Semigroups, *Thai Journal of Mathematics*, 12 (2014), 455-464.
- [26] M. K. Sen and N. K. Saha. On Γ -semigroup I, *Bull. Cal. Math. Soc.* 78 (1986), 181-186.
- [27] M. K. Sen and A. Seth. On po- Γ -semigroups, *Bull. Calcutta Math. Soc.*, 85 (1993), 445-450.
- [28] J. Tang. Characterization of ordered semigroups by of $(\in, \in \vee q)$ -fuzzy ideals, *World Acad. of Sci., Eng. and Tech.*, 6 (2012), 518 – 530.
- [29] L. A. Zadeh. Fuzzy sets, *Information and Control*, 8 (1965), 338 – 353.

AHSAN MAHBOOB

DEPARTMENT OF MATHEMATICS, ALIGARH MUSLIM UNIVERSITY, ALIGARH-202002, INDIA

Email address: khanahsan56@gmail.com

NOOR MOHAMMAD KHAN

DEPARTMENT OF MATHEMATICS, ALIGARH MUSLIM UNIVERSITY, ALIGARH-202002, INDIA

Email address: nm.khan123@yahoo.co.in